

Final Program

أدنوك
ADNOC

SOCIETY OF
CORE ANALYSTS

October 9-13, 2023 - Abu Dhabi

Advanced SCAL for Carbon
Storage & CO₂ Utilization

From the 2023 President

Dear Colleagues and Friends

On behalf of the Society and the Board of Directors, It is a great pleasure to welcome you to the Society of Core Analysts (SCA) International Symposium 2023 in Abu Dhabi, UAE!

There is an ever-increasing focus on climate change and emissions from burning fossil fuels. Increasing global temperatures and contiguous weather-related disasters are now part of daily conversations and on top of the agenda for policy makers. The subsurface is both part of the problem and the solution, being the origin of the fossil fuels currently being burnt and a storage site for unwanted CO₂. There is therefore no coincidence that the theme of both last year and this year symposium is focused on the storage of CO₂. If we are going to reach the goals of the Paris agreement, a gigantic scale-up of the current levels of CO₂ sequestration is inevitable. This brings along new challenges for core analysis – challenges I am certain that our community can tackle. I also believe our community is ready to take on these new challenges.

The SCA symposium is an important meeting place for the core analysis community. The relatively small size, without parallel sessions, promotes interactions that connect and build relationships. It also brings together scientists and engineers from both academia and industry workers. I would therefore like to thank all the people that enable this yearly event. In particular, the VP Technology, Cyril Caubit and his technical committee, who have put down a lot of work in the review process and putting together the scientific program. The VP Arrangement, Ali AlSumaiti, who has done a tremendous job in organizing the venue and the social program. Off course our SCA Executive Director, Melanie Young, who is always our steady hand on the helm. Last, but not least, all the participants who are contributing to this symposium through papers, presentations, and discussions.

I am convinced we will have another excellent symposium this year with plenty of good discussion and good socialization. I look forward to seeing you all in Abu Dhabi!

Carl Fredrik Berg

SCA President

From the 2023 VP Arrangements

Asalam Alikm All and Welcome back to Abu Dhabi!

On behalf of the SCA and the Organizing Committee, we are absolutely thrilled to extend our warmest welcome to all the attendees of the 2023 SCA Annual Symposium as we return to Abu Dhabi after a significant hiatus of 15 years! We are confident that each one of you is eagerly anticipating your visit to our remarkable capital city. Abu Dhabi is not only the proud home of an aspiring global financial center but also a burgeoning innovation hub, a leading energy producer, and an extraordinary world-class tourist destination and cultural center.

As many of you may already know, the UAE has designated the year 2023 as the Year of Sustainability, and the central theme of this symposium revolves around pioneering solutions that can expedite our progress toward achieving a net-zero carbon footprint. It's noteworthy that Abu Dhabi has the world's first sustainable urban community, 'Masdar City,' a highly recommended destination where you can immerse yourself in a sustainable lifestyle.

Moreover, Abu Dhabi has been honored twice with the distinction of being the safest city in the world. The Emirate, sprawling across 67,340 Km², is gracefully nestled along the picturesque coastline of the Arabian Gulf. It encompasses over 200 islands, many of which offer breathtaking sandy beaches. Notable among these are Yas Island, a world-renowned entertainment destination, and Saadiyat Island, celebrated for its cultural attractions, including the esteemed Louvre Abu Dhabi. We strongly encourage you to explore the abundance of cultural and adventurous activities that Abu Dhabi has to offer by visiting www.experienceabudhabi.ae.

Our Young Professionals' event will take place at the AlForsan Sports Resort, where participants will have the opportunity to indulge in extreme adventures, featuring a world-class karting circuit built to the highest standards and an exhilarating paintball arena. Following these activities, there will be ample time for socializing with industry professionals in a more relaxed setting.

Lastly, don't miss out on the one-day field trip to Jabal Hafit, situated in Al-Ain, approximately 180 Km away from our venue. This presents an exciting opportunity to gain insights from our experts on topics such as carbonate rock structural styles, fractures, and the assessment of potential CO₂ storage.

In conclusion, we wish to express our sincere gratitude to our generous sponsors and dedicated vendors for their invaluable support, with a special acknowledgment of ADNOC for their unwavering commitment to hosting this event. We extend our heartfelt appreciation to the authors, technical committee members, and volunteers who have collectively contributed to making this event another success and a truly memorable experience. Lastly, a very special thank you goes to Melanie Young, who has been the backbone of this organization.

Salam Alikum, and we extend our warmest wishes to all for an enjoyable and memorable stay in Abu Dhabi!

Ali M. AlSumaiti,

VP Arrangement

From the 2023 VP Technology

Dear Colleagues and Friends,

Welcome to the 2023 SCA International Symposium in Abu Dhabi, UAE!

We are going to work together these four days on core analysis in general but also try to focus this year on “carbon storage & CO2 Utilisation” We started this year with a total of 86 abstracts submitted. I want to thank all the authors that submitted abstracts whether they were accepted or not, your contribution is the heart of our conference. After a careful selection and review of all the papers we have 34 Orals and 30 Posters planned for this year. I want to thank the entire technical committee for their commitment, their attention to details, their willingness to make every single paper a better paper after the review than it was before. Thank you all, authors, and reviewers, you are the technical excellence of SCA.

In the short course this year, we will cover “Advanced SCAL for Carbon Storage & CO2 Utilisation”. I want to thank the entire team who prepared this course: Shehadeh Masalmeh, Mohammad Piri, Lisa Lun and Sam Krevor. I hope this course will be interesting and pedagogic for our community.

Special thanks for Melanie Young, our SCA Executive Director. She has been invaluable in putting together the program this year.

I look forward to seeing you in Abu Dhabi!

Cyril CAUBIT PhD

SCA VP of Technology

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2023 Technical Committee

The SCA Technical Committee is the backbone of the Society of Core Analysts. Its members rank and evaluate the submitted abstracts and the technical quality of the manuscripts. In the review of each individual manuscript and in-depth discussions with the authors, many hours are spent until a manuscript is accepted. In many cases, the interaction between authors and TC members leads to a higher quality of individual manuscripts. As a result, the annual SCA symposia are packed with high-quality presentations. For this, sincere acknowledgement go to this year's Technical Committee members:

Adam Moss	JinHong Chen	Stacey Althaus
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Emad Walid Al Shalabi	Olga Vizika	Rudolf Held
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Felix Feldmann	Omid Karoussi	Shannon Eichmann
Franck Nono	Patrick Egermann	Stacey Althaus
Gerald Hamon	Roland Lenormand	Stephanie Perry
Harry Xie	Rudolf Held	Stefano Pruno
Hassan Mahani	Ryan Armstrong	Steffen Berg
Hendrik Rohler	Shannon Eichmann	Subhash Ayirala
Holger Ott	Shouxiang Mark Ma	Will Richardson
Hyung Kwak	Souhail Youssef	
Issa Abu Shiekah		
James Howard		
Jim Funk		

Technical Achievement Darcy Award Recipient Shehadeh Masalmeh

Shehadeh Masalmeh is currently working as a senior advisor reservoir engineer and a SCAL and EOR expert, with more than 25 years' experience in both Shell and ADNOC. Shehadeh obtained PhD in physics from Leiden University.

In his career, he has developed extensive expertise on carbonate reservoirs, SCAL, wettability, reservoir characterization and development, modelling of oil in transition zone, modelling waterflooding in heterogeneous reservoirs. He has also developed extensive expertise in a wide range of EOR techniques including gas based EOR, low salinity flooding, chemical EOR and hybrid EOR processes.

In his current job in ADNOC, Shehadeh developed ADNOC EOR strategy and roadmap, developed and designed the EOR R&D program to mature new EOR techniques for high temperature and high salinity light oil carbonate reservoirs. He developed hybrid EOR processes such as Simultaneous Injection of Miscible Gas and Polymer (SIMGAP), Simultaneous Injection of Water and Polymer (SIWAP), and Simultaneous Water and Gas Injection (SWAG). These pioneering EOR technologies are going through different stages of field developments with significant early successes including world's first polymer injectivity field tests in high temperature and high salinity carbonates.

Shehadeh has developed SCAL best practices from lab measurements, interpretation to field Implementation during his work in Shell and ADNOC, pioneered the work on including capillary pressure hysteresis into dynamic modelling workflow and demonstrated its significant impact on understanding water flooding of heterogeneous mixed-wet to oil-wet carbonate reservoirs. He developed a relative permeability and capillary Pressure hysteresis model where the Pc hysteresis model has been recently implemented in the main industry commercial simulators. He has developed and taught training courses on SCAL, Sor and EOR.

Shehadeh has been awarded 2015 SPE Regional Award for Reservoir Description and Dynamics in the Middle East and has notably won best paper awards at different SCA conferences. He has published over 110 papers in journals and SPE and SCA conferences on various aspects of multiphase flow in porous Media and EOR.

Special thanks to ADNOC

On behalf of the entire SCA Symposium organizing committee and participants, we extend our heartfelt gratitude for your invaluable support in sponsoring our event in Abu Dhabi. Your unwavering commitment, both financially and through the dedication of your manpower, has played a pivotal role in making this symposium a resounding success.

Your financial support has allowed us to create an enriching and memorable experience for all attendees. It has facilitated the seamless organization of workshops, presentations, and networking opportunities that have greatly contributed to the dissemination of knowledge in our industry. Thanks to your generous contribution, we have been able to invite esteemed speakers and experts, ensuring that the symposium lived up to its reputation as a platform for cutting-edge discussions and innovation.

Moreover, your provision of manpower resources has been instrumental in the smooth execution of the event. Your team's dedication, professionalism, and expertise have been invaluable in handling various logistical aspects, from registration and event coordination to technical support. Your commitment to excellence has not gone unnoticed, and it has left a lasting positive impression on our participants.

Once again, we extend our sincere appreciation to ADNOC for your unwavering support. Your partnership has been instrumental in the success of the SCA Symposium, and we look forward to continuing this collaboration in the future, as we work together to advance knowledge and innovation in our field.

With warm regards,

Melanie Young
Executive Director
SCA Symposium Organizing Committee

The Venue

Enjoy a refined stay on the waterfront at InterContinental® Abu Dhabi, located at the city's dynamic heart. This five-star hotel invites you in with light-filled, sophisticated spaces, award-winning dining, premium wellness facilities and 390 spacious guest rooms bathed in the panoramic city and coastal views. InterContinental Abu Dhabi also features outstanding meeting and events spaces, an elegant Club InterContinental lounge and personalized concierge services to keep you 'in the know' about this exciting destination. Gaze over the city skyline from your room, stroll along the Corniche, dine by the twinkling lights of the terrace, or dip into the sparkling waters - at InterContinental Abu Dhabi, you've assured a memorable stay. InterContinental Abu Dhabi is known as one of the landmark hotels in Abu Dhabi.

Short Courses – Monday 9th, 8:50 a.m. – 12:30 p.m.

Short Workshop: Advanced SCAL for Carbon Storage & Utilization

A special thanks to the presenters who helped put this short workshop together; Shehadeh Masalmeh, Mohammad Piri, Lisa Lun and Sam Krevor

Coffee and tea will be available during breaks. Lunch will be provided to attendees.

Short Course is Kindly Sponsored by: ADNOC

Opening Reception –Monday 9th, 5:30p.m. - 8:30 p.m.

The Opening “Icebreaker” Reception will be held in the Sunset Room. Snacks and drinks will be served to foster a relaxed atmosphere to meet and greet both old and new colleagues.

Dress Code: Business casual

Kindly Sponsored by: ADNOC

Technical Sessions – Monday 9th, Tuesday 10th, Wednesday 11th and Thursday 12th, 8:15 a.m. - 5 p.m.

(With the exception for start at 1:30 p.m. on Monday).

Oral presentations: The Symposium will offer 34 oral presentations, 25 minute presentations followed by 5 minutes for discussion.

Poster sessions: The symposium will offer 30 posters, distributed in three poster sessions.

Young Professionals Event – Tuesday 10th, 5:00-9:00 p.m.

Al Forsan International Sport Resort LLC

Arrival at Al Forsan reception where guests will be greeted by Al Forsan, we will start with a light coffee break and then enjoy some Karting and Paintball followed by dinner.

Kindly Sponsored by: Core Labs

Awards Gala Dinner – Wednesday 11th, 6:30 - 9:30 pm

The gala dinner will be held at the InterContinental Hotel.

Dress code: Business Casual.

Gala Dinner is Kindly Sponsored by: ADNOC

Optional Field Trip – Friday September 13th, 9:00 a.m.- 6:30 p.m.

Optional Friday Field Trip

Jabal Hafit Mountain-Al Ain

Leave Intercontinental Hotel at 7:00 am on Friday, Oct. 13th

- Transportation and lunch provided.
- Arrival to Al-Ain: 9:00 am – 9:30 am
- Safety Briefing and Geological Tour: 9:30 am – 2:00 pm
- Lunch will be served by end of tour: 2:30 pm
- Departure back to Abu Dhabi at 4:30 pm
- Arrival to Hotel at 6:30 pm

Kindly Sponsored by: ADNOC

Publication of Proceedings

The proceedings are prepared in online format and login details will be given at the Symposium to all registered participants.

www.SCAweb.org

The SCA has decided to no longer carry printed copies of the proceedings.

Exhibition Hours

Monday: 8:30 a.m. – 5:30 p.m.	*Exhibition Build-up starts at 8:30am
Tuesday: 8:30 a.m. – 5:00 p.m.	
Wednesday: 8:30 a.m. – 5:00 p.m.	
Thursday: 8:30 a.m. – 5:00 p.m	*Exhibition Break-down can start after the afternoon break and complete by 5pm.

Exhibitor

Abu Dhabi National Oil Company (ADNOC) - ADNOC is a leading diversified energy group, wholly owned by the Abu Dhabi Government. Our network of fully integrated businesses operates across the energy value chain, helping us to responsibly meet the demands of an ever-changing energy market. Already in the top tier of the lowest carbon intensity oil and gas producers in the world, we are taking significant steps to make today's energy cleaner while investing in the clean energies of tomorrow, strengthening our position as a reliable and responsible global energy provider. We are allocating an initial \$15 billion to advance and accelerate lower-carbon solutions, investing in new energies and decarbonization technologies to enable our net zero by 2045 ambition and our commitment to zero methane emissions by 2030.

AMETEK Chandler Engineering – AMETEK Chandler Engineering produces the highest quality instruments and measurement systems for the Oil and Gas Industry. Our portfolio includes Quizix precision pumps used in core flooding (NEW models available!), SCAL, EOR, and other fluid delivery applications, the 6100 Formation Response (formation damage) systems, Core flood/EOR flow systems, custom core flow systems for Steady State/Unsteady State permeability measurements, and the Chandler 3000 Series PVT systems for phase behavior studies.

Core Technical Services - CTS is a Subsurface Analysis and Visualisation Specialist - We have a global presence in the Core digitisation market, together with our trusted partners and clients across the globe we have already begun the digital transformation. Core Technical Services has a great reputation for providing core analysis services and products worldwide. What sets us apart from the rest is our ability to customize our offering to customers' needs, as well as our fantastic team of specialists.

Our strength lies not only within our internal team, but also with our extensive network of associate subject matter experts (SMEs) in a wide range of disciplines, including reservoir engineering, geomechanics, coring, well planning, and much more. If you need a core-related skill we don't have in-house, we can source it.

Through our partnership with Craytive Technologies. We are showcasing the BaselineZ platform at this Symposium. BaselineZ is where core analysis and the sub-surface meet the Metaverse. The power of the platform has many facets but includes the ability to integrate and manage all types of core and sub-surface data and imagery in the Virtual Core Shed and Virtual Data Room - from nano-CT, thin section, to the whole core, well, field, basin, or region. It maximizes the value of collaboration as team members can join virtual meetings from anywhere there is an internet connection worldwide – all appearing in the same virtual space as avatars. At Core Technical Services our enthusiasm for core is second to none – please do come past of booth or talk to us anytime. We endorse all and every service provider exhibiting at the SCA and will promote any service & service provider **we believe provides innovative and cost-effective solutions to our mutual clients.**

DCI Corporation – DCI offers innovative solutions to your core testing requirements. From turnkey systems to system components we can help you with your laboratory needs. DCI designs and manufactures both custom and standard core holders, accumulators, syringe pumps, acoustic separators, core flood systems, electrical resistivity systems, rock mechanics systems and much more. Stop by our booth to see how DCI can help you make better measurements on core properties.

EPSLOG - Founded in 2005 by engineers with unique expertise in rock cutting and drilling mechanics, Epslog is an independent company specialized in delivering expert and tailored services in rock testing and drilling data interpretation. Epslog is proud to serve the energy transition with rock digitalization technologies tailored for sustainable analysis of cores and drill cuttings, with applications ranging from CCS projects to mining industrial minerals.

GeoTek - GeoTek - Geotek is a group of companies specialising in the non-destructive analysis of geological cores. We supply our range of Multi-Sensor Core Logger (MSCL), hyperspectral imaging, and X-ray CT systems that use multiple geophysical and geochemical sensors to rapidly and automatically gather measurements on sediment or rock cores. The rugged nature of the equipment makes it suitable for use in either an onshore laboratory/repository environment or onboard survey and drilling vessels. Stop by our booth and discuss our dedicated core plug and core flood CT systems, and find out about our brand-new multi-client dataset for pre-salt reservoirs in Brazil!

Green Imaging Technologies, Inc – Green Imaging Technologies is the industry leader in NMR rock core analysis. Our software is the backbone of the Oxford GeoSpec line of NMR Rock Core Analyzers, which are used by all major oil producers, oil service companies and the most active research institutes worldwide. Our customers have access to exclusive, patented measurements including NMR capillary pressure and quantitative saturation profiles. Our team of experts are focused on rock core analysis, and as such have developed relationships with the most respected researchers and experts in the NMR rock core analysis field. We are always looking for new NMR applications and look forward to talking to current and potential NMR users about how NMR can help them solve their reservoir puzzles.

HOT Microfluidics GmbH - Based in Goslar at the Energy Research Centre of Lower Saxony (Germany), HOT Microfluidics focuses on experiments with hydrogen, carbon dioxide, and gas mixtures in compliance with the highest HSE standards. As a leading High-Pressure, high-temperature (HPHT) technology provider for PVT, IOR/EOR, and New Energy applications, HOT Microfluidics helps Energy companies and research organisations globally speed up lab routines at a significantly reduced cost. (www.fluidicslab.com)

Math2Market GmbH - Math2Market GmbH - Math2Market develops the GeoDict software to provide a complete solution to our clients comprising software, support, project work, user training, and customized software development. The Digital Rock Physics and Digital Core Analysis (DRP-DCA) suite of GeoDict, in combination with imaging capabilities, is a purpose-built tool that enables its users to perform the entire workflow digitally and in-house with unmatched fast runtimes, handling of extremely large data sets, and low hardware requirements. Latest applications of GeoDict are the simulation of two-phase flow with consideration of the entire hysteresis cycle or the digital analysis of rocks for CO₂ sequestration techniques and storage mechanisms.

PremierCorex - Premier Corex: Global Leader in Rock and Fluid Data Solutions
Premier Corex aggregates, generates, and applies rock and fluid data to enhance understanding, exploration, and resource development. With world-class experts, labs, and platforms, we provide accessible data and effective solutions for our clients. Our innovative business models enable cost-effective data generation and shared workspaces to address common challenges. We tackle today's energy industry challenges and future resource opportunities by preserving and curating subsurface samples and data. Premier Corex stands out with its comprehensive approach, setting us apart from testing-focused laboratories.

Prores As— Prores is a Norwegian independent and private corporation built on knowledge and with an ambition to bridge the gap from ideas to solutions. Prores consists of an integrated team of researchers and engineers with an extensive network offering petroleum expertise, technology, and software development. Prores offer high quality solutions for petroleum asset operations. All products are developed in-house in close cooperation with industrial partners. The latest spin-offs from Prores are At-the-Bit company, WellGuard and WellStarter where Prores remains a majority owner. WellGuard technology is a wireline logging tool for precision measurements of cement barrier integrity through multiple consecutive casings to detect debonding, micro-annuli, cracks, and fluid channels prior to P&A operations. Wellstarter HIPlot is a wireless downhole flow monitoring solution based on heat pulses released into the well stream providing the inflow profile of oil, gas, and water in producing wells. At-the-Bit Mud Loss Control is a new approach for while-drilling treatment of mud loss during drilling operations. The innovative solution is based on converting the circulating mud to a swellable pill downhole that reacts with the mud for sealing off formation fractures. The Sendra software is the market leading software for experimental history matching and SCAL analysis and currently works in native-cloud solution with additional new features on SCAL analog and modeling. For more information on our solutions and services, please visit our website at www.prores.no.

Qmineral – Qmineral is an independent material test laboratory and one of the most important mineralogy/XRD labs worldwide. We were the first lab to win the “Reynolds cup” (aka the World Championship of quantitative mineralogy) for two consecutive times. We are specialized in the analysis of clay bearing samples and the detailed structural analysis of a rock’s clay minerals.
Qmineral has just launched its new service for quantitative mineralogy, named HSMQ (High Speed Mineralogical Analysis). HSMQ is an FTIR-based tool to quantify the mineralogy of a sample very accurately and very quickly - about 40 times faster than with XRD, allowing you to characterize a virtually unlimited amount of samples in a very short time, also onsite.

RS Systems – RS Systems is an independent Norwegian based company, which develops, designs and manufactures laboratory set-ups for advanced laboratory analysis of rock and fluid properties. RS Systems expertise has been developed through several decades of combined experience from the core and fluid analysis business, as well as from focused research activities related to optimizing and improving oil and gas production globally.

RS Systems module based systems combine innovative solutions with well known technology and components from petroleum related laboratory analysis.

Our products apply state-of-the-art technology in the laboratory, with heavy focus on in-situ saturation monitoring, using gamma and X-ray attenuations. In addition, through focused process monitoring and automatic data acquisition, RS Systems secures smooth integration of laboratory data from the laboratory to our clients geo- and reservoir modeling tools.

RS Systems' products are being used by Oil Companies, Research Institutions and Service Laboratories globally to provide vital data for the interpretation and estimation of;

Hydrocarbons In-Place (OIIP & GIIP), CO₂ storage potential, Production profile and total reserves from traditional displacement mechanisms, Production profile from advanced displacement mechanisms (Improved Oil Recovery, IOR).

RS Systems is sharing a booth with ResBridge - ResBridge is an independent Norwegian company developing RockSys®, an innovative suite of analysis applications. The suite includes applications that link laboratory measurements of core data to reservoir models and simulations. RockSys® streamlines ingestion, enrichment and integration of rock data into company databases, providing key-input for reservoir modelling. The procedures established in the automated workflow involves the process of standardising, structuring, quality assuring, contextualization and making business-critical rock data available for a wide range of subsurface disciplines such as: Petrophysics, Reservoir engineering, Geomechanics, Geology.

Schlumberger – We are SLB, a global technology company driving energy innovation.

We've always built our business around our customers and their endeavors; they are at the center of everything we do. Bringing together talented people from all over the globe, we're working on the industry's most complex and pressing challenges to anticipate and align with our customers' needs. We want to be their performance partner of choice.

To achieve this goal and deliver the best results, we must combine our unique talents and our collective expertise—not just within SLB but by working closely with our suppliers, contractors, and business partners.

We are industry leaders because of our exceptional and talented people. They are the core that drives our purpose and integrity, which fuel our belief that everyone should have the opportunity to reach their greatest potential. Ever-evolving and constantly innovating, we transcend every cultural and technological boundary set before us. Indeed, it is our diversity that makes us stronger. Together, we achieve more.

We are SLB, and we are leading the energy industry forward—together.

Stratum Reservoir - Stratum Reservoir are globally operating applied geoscience specialists, who through decades of experience and all our services enable our customers to discover and develop sustainable energy resources.

We support divesture strategies and energy resource investment through the analysis and interpretation of rocks and fluids in our laboratories worldwide. We specialize in reservoir characterization that helps to deliver deep scientific insights across the subsurface industry.

Vinci Technologies/Floxlab - Vinci Technologies is an engineering company specializing in the design and manufacturing of highly specific instruments for rock and fluid analysis, as well as high-pressure metering pumps. Our product range includes rigs for measuring relative permeability and capillary pressure, conducting PVT studies, and performing triaxial rock compression tests. These versatile tools open up new market opportunities to address challenges in carbon sequestration and hydrogen storage.

Vindum Engineering Inc. - MANUFACTURER OF PRECISION HIGH PRESSURE PULSE-FREE PUMPS and VALVES

NEW VIPR Series Pumps: Large Volume Cylinder Pumps

- Easily upgrade to Continuous Pulse-Free Flow with 2 pumps
- Syringe Piston Design with Cylinder Wash Area
- CV Valves Standard
- VPware Software Included
- Gas or Liquids, including CO₂

VP Series Pumps: High Precision, Continuous Pulse-Free Metering Pumps

- Latest generation design: lower cost, higher performance
- Models up to 25,000 psi
- Ambient Temperature or High Temperature (up to 160C) Options
- Gas or Liquids, including CO₂

CV Valves: Constant-Volume, High-Pressure Valves

- Air activation
- High Temperature applications (up to 300C)
- Gas or Liquids, 2-Way and 3-Way Models

MV Hastelloy Valves & Fittings: Modular Manual Valve System

- Mountable, compact design saves space
- O-ring seals: replaceable, various seal materials
- Lower Cost Hastelloy Design
- In-stock for immediate delivery

Hastelloy Tubing: In stock for immediate delivery

Booth Layout

1. Green Imaging Technologies, Inc
2. QMineral
- 3 and 4. Schlumberger
- 5.
6. Core Technical Services
7. DCI Corporation
8. AMETEK Chandler Engineering
9. Math2Market GmbH
10. Premier Corex
11. HOT Microfluidics
12. EPSLOG
13. Geotek Ltd
14. Prores AS
- 15.
16. Vinci Technologies/Floxlab
17. Stratum Reservoir
18. RS Systems
- 19 and 20. Vindum Engineering
21. ADNOC

Short Course Program

Advanced SCAL for Carbon Storage & CO₂ Utilization

MONDAY, October 9, 2023

Short Workshop: Advanced SCAL for Carbon Storage & CO ₂ Utilization	
Moderator: Cyril Caubit and Ali Alsumaiti	
8:30 – 8:50	Welcome and safety moment
8:50 – 9:40	How Can SCAL Help to Optimize CCS and CO ₂ -EOR Projects Presenter: Shehadeh Masalmeh
9:40 – 10:30	Two- and three-phase relative permeability measurements: advances, challenges, and lessons learned Presenter: Mohammad Piri
10:30 – 10:50	Coffee Break Kindly Sponsored by: AMETEK Chandler Engineering
10:50 – 11:40	Supercritical CO ₂ and brine relative permeability, critical review and consistent analyses Presenter: Lisa Lun
11:40 – 12:30	Advanced applications in core analysis for CO ₂ storage: Digital rocks, wetting, and heterogeneity Presenter: Sam Krevor
12:30 – 1:30	Lunch Kindly Sponsored by: Chevron

Technical Program

Monday, October 9, 2023

7:30 – 5:00	Registration Desk Open
1:30 – 3:00	<p>Session 1: SCAL for Carbon Storage & Utilization (1)</p> <p>Chairs: Lisa Lun and Sam Krevor</p>
SCA001	<p>Measurement of Trapped Gas Saturation in Carbonate Rock: Comparing 2-phase and 3-phase data to Support CCS and CO₂ EOR Projects</p> <p>Shehadeh Masalmeh, Amir Farzaneh, Mehran Sohrabi, Ali Al-Mesmari and Mohammad Al-Hammadi</p>
SCA002	<p>CO₂-Brine Relative Permeability Measurements at Reservoir Conditions: how to reconcile SS and USS methods?</p> <p>Matthieu Mascle, Ameline Oisel, Per Kristian Munkeud, Einar Ebeltoft, Olivier Lopez, Colin Pryme and Souhail Youssef</p>
SCA003	<p>A Review and Discussion on Laboratory Investigations Involving Supercritical CO₂ for Storage</p> <p>Mahsan Basafa, Omid Mohammadzadeh and Lesley Anne James</p>
3:00 - 3:30	<p>Coffee Break</p> <p>Kindly Sponsored by: AMETEK Chandler Engineering</p>
3:30- 5:00	<p>Session 2: Improved SCAL Techniques and Interpretation (1) NMR</p> <p>Chairs: Olivier Lopez and Hyung Tae Kwak</p>
SCA004	<p>Stochastic Interpretation of CO₂-Brine Primary Displacement in Heterogeneous Carbonate Rocks</p> <p>Omidreza Amrollahinasab, Boris Jammerneegg, Siroos Azizmohammadi and Holger Ott</p>
SCA005	<p>Bulk saturation measurement of water and oil in porous media using ¹³C and ¹H magnetic resonance</p>

	Naser Ansaribaranghar, Mohammad Sadegh Zamiri, Laura Romero-Zerón, Florea Marica, Andres Ramirez, Derrick Green, Benjamin Nicot and Bruce J. Balcom
SCA006	Hybrid Drainage Technique application on bimodal limestone Victor Fernandes, Franck Nono, Benjamin Nicot, Fabrice Pairoys, Henri Bertin, Jean Lachaud and Cyril Caubit
5:30 - 8:30	Opening Reception “Icebreaker Reception” Kindly Sponsored by: ADNOC
Tuesday, October 10, 2023	
8:00 – 5:00	Registration Desk Open
8:30 - 9:30	Session 3: Wettability Chairs: Stefano Pruno and Carl Frederik Berg
SCA007	Impact of Dopants on SCAL Experiments, Phase I Fabrice Pairoys, Cyril Caubit, Laurent Rochereau, Ata Nepesov, Quentin Danielczick, Nicolas Agenet and Franck Nono
SCA008	Optimization of core restoration procedure based on adsorption of polar crude oil components onto sandstone and carbonate rocks Aleksandr Mamonov, Skule Strand, Tina Puntervold, Panagiotis Aslanidis and Iván Darío Piñerez Torrijos
9:30 – 10:00	Exhibitor Presentations
10:00 - 10:30	Coffee Break Kindly Sponsored by: Aramco America
10:30 – 12:00	Session 4: SCAL for Carbon Storage & Utilization (2) Chairs: Einar Ebeltoft and Emad Walid Al Shalabi

SCA009	A Laboratory Investigation of Enhanced Gas Recovery by CO ₂ Injection Chris Jones, Mike Spearing, Maynard Marrion, Arief Maulana and Frans Silitonga
SCA010	CO ₂ /Brine Relative Permeability Estimation Using Effective Rock/Fluid Properties: A Machine Learning-Based Approach Fatemeh Reisi, Omid Mohammadzadeh and Lesley Anne James
SCA011	Laboratory Assessment of CO ₂ Storage in Oil Reservoirs through Converting Waterfloods to Carbonated Waterfloods Mehran Sohrabi, Amir Farzaneh and Almohannad AlGhamdi
12:00 - 1:00	Lunch Kindly Sponsored by: TOTALenergies
1:00 – 1:30	Poster Presentations (SCA035-SCA044)
1:30 - 2:30	Coffee Break and Poster Session (SCA035-SCA044) Kindly Sponsored by: Aramco America
2:30 – 3:00	Exhibitor presentations
3:00 – 4:30	Session 5: Pore Scale Imaging and Modelling (1) Chairs: Souhail Youssef and Mohamed Regaieg
SCA012	Derivation of a representative elementary volume (REV) for upscaled two-phase flow in porous media. James E. McClure, Ming Fan, Steffen Berg, Ryan T. Armstrong, Carl Fredrik Berg, Zhe Li and Thomas Ramstad
SCA013	Pore-scale comparisons of primary drainage techniques on non-water-wet reservoir rocks Franck Nono, Fabrice Pairoys, Victor Fernandes and Cyril Caubit

SCA014	A priori simulation of relative permeabilities of intact subsamples of tight oil shale from a hydraulic fracturing play G.Peter Matthews and Katie Jones
5:00 – 9:00 p.m.	Young Professional Event Kindly Sponsored by: Core Labs
Wednesday, October 11, 2023	
8:15 – 5:00	Registration Desk Open
8:30 – 10:00	Session 6: SCAL for Carbon Storage & Utilization (3) Chairs: Shehadeh Maslameh and Mohammad Piri
SCA015	Steady-state supercritical CO ₂ and brine relative permeability measurements at different pressure conditions. Bo Gao, Elizabeth Lyons, Daulet Magzymov, Larry Poore, Gloria Besil, Stacy Richardson and Lisa Lun
SCA016	SCAL model for CCS – Insights from the first commercial CO ₂ project on the Norwegian Continental Shelf, the Northern Lights Einar Ebeltoft, Marion Recordon, Renata Meneguolo, Jørgen Gausdal Jacobsen, Reza Askarinezhad and Richy Pitman
SCA017	Risk of permeability impairment due to CO ₂ hydrates formation in sandstone: an experimental investigation using X-Ray Radiography Matthieu Mascle, Ameline Oisel, Nicolas Gland, Raymond Jellema, Luc Pauget and Souhail Youssef
10:00 - 10:30	Coffee Break Kindly Sponsored by: Math2Market
10:30 – 12:00	Session 7: Improved SCAL Techniques and Interpretation (2) – NMR Chairs: Jinhong Chen and Benjamin Nicot

SCA018	Direct Hydrocarbon Saturation Imaging in Porous Media with ¹³ C Naser Ansaribaranghar, Mohammad Sadegh Zamiri, Laura Romero-Zerón, Florea Marica, Andres Ramirez, Derrick Green, Benjamin Nicot and Bruce J. Balcom
SCA019	Impact of Dual Matrix Porosity in Sandstone on Fluid Distribution and Flow Properties Yingxue Wang and Serge V. Galley
SCA020	An integrated SCAL study for estimating wettability and relative permeability Raheleh Farokhpoor, Andrew Fogden and Egil Boye Petersen
12:00 - 1:00	Lunch Kindly Sponsored by: Stratum Reservoir
1:00 – 2:00	Session 8: Unconventionals and Source Rocks Chairs: Harry Xie and Matthias Halisch
SCA021	Laboratory Measurement of Total Porosity and Fluid Saturations for Unconventional Tight Rocks: Methodologies, Challenges, and Comparison Min Cheng, Rayvan Watson, Alberto Latuff, Aaron Rodriguez, Peter Kaufman, Joshua Miller, Rafael A. Mendoza, Elizabeth Krukowski and Robert Cole
SCA022	Delineating Light Hydrocarbon Configuration in Source Rocks from NMR Relaxation Mechanism of Nano-Confined Fluids Jin-Hong Chen, Stacey Althaus, Chao Liu and Mohammed Boudjatit
2:00 – 2:30	Poster Presentations (SCA045-SCA054)
2:30 - 3:30	Coffee Break and Poster Session (SCA045-SCA054) Kindly Sponsored by: Math2Market

3:30 – 4:30	Session 9: Displacement Mechanisms/EOR/IOR Chairs: Ali Hassan Al Mesmari and Issa Abu Shiekah
SCA023	Foam-Assisted Enhanced Oil Recovery: Bridging the Gap between Theory and Practice Jinesh Machale, Dorcas Annung Akrong, Omid Mohammadzadeh, Ali Telmadarreie, Anand Yethiraj and Lesley Anne James
SCA024	Positive Capillary Forces: The Key for optimized Oil Recovery in Low-Permeable Cores Md Ashraful Islam Khan, Skule Strand, Tina Puntervold and Aleksandr Mamonov
6:30 – 9:30	Gala Dinner Kindly Sponsored by: ADNOC
Thursday, October 12, 2023	
8:30 – 3:00	Registration Desk Open
8:30 - 10:00	Session 10: Pore Scale Imaging and Modelling (2) Chairs: Ahmed Al Ratrout and Christoph Arns
SCA025	Prediction of wetting condition in a reservoir rock using coupled digital rock and molecular dynamics simulation. Ashraful Islam, Joshua D. Moore, Rafael Salazar-Tio, Guangyuan Sun, Andrew Fager, Bernd Crouse, Sabine Schweizer, Kwan Skinner and Lalitha Subramanian
SCA026	Prediction of relative permeability and fast wettability assessment using Digital Rock Physics: An operational study on a Reservoir Sandstone Mohamed Regaieg, Titly Farhana Faisal, Franck Nono, Fabrice Pairoys, Victor Fernandes and Cyril Caubit
SCA027	Multiscale computational models for simulating relative permeability in complex carbonate rock sample

	Guangyuan Sun, Rafael Salazar-Tio, Jingjing Yang, Hiroshi Otomo, Ganapathi Balasubramanian, Ashraful Islam, Andrew Fager, Bernd Crouse, Raoyang Zhang and Josephina Schembre-McCabe
10:00 - 10:30	Coffee Break Kindly Sponsored by - ADNOC
10:30 – 12:00	Session 11: Improved SCAL Techniques and Interpretation (3) – NMR Chairs: Mohamed Ibrahim Al Hammadi and Asmund Haugen
SCA028	Pore Size Measurement in Core Plugs with Magnetic Resonance based on Brownstein Tarr Relaxation Theory Peiyuan Yan, Florin Marica, Benjamin Nicot, Derrick Green and Bruce J. Balcom
SCA029	Derivation of Waxman-Smiths and Indonesia parameters from Co-Cw experiments: a new perspective Stefano Rossini and Nicola Bona
SCA030	The Effect of Different LET Parameters Combination in Relative Permeability towards Core and Field-Scale Simulations Wilson Wiranda, Kurdistan Chawsin and Rolf Myhr
12:00 – 12:30	Business Meeting
12:30 - 1:30	Lunch Kindly Sponsored by: Schlumberger
1:30 – 2:00	Poster Presentations (SCA055-SCA064)
2:00 - 3:00	Coffee Break and Poster Session (SCA055-SCA064) Kindly Sponsored by: ADNOC

3:00 – 5:00	Session 12: Laboratory Core Analysis Chairs: Jules Reed and Mike Spearing
SCA031	Measurement of Gas Condensate Relative Permeabilities utilizing NMR and MRI Technologies Michael Rauschhuber, Jon Burger, Josephina Schembre-McCabe, Elton Yang and Boqin Sun
SCA032	Diffusion measurements with hydrogen and methane through reservoir rock samples Julia Michelsen, Nils Langanke, Birger Hagemann, Sebastian Hogeweg and Leonhard Ganzer
SCA033	Investigation of Temperature Characteristics of Secondary Organic Matter and Hydrocarbons in the Early Jurassic Marrat Formation using Laboratory NMR Techniques Z. Harry Xie, Phil Hawley, Abdul Mohsen Al Mershed, Mihira Narayan Acharya, Nilotpaul Neog, Matthias Appel and Seán Dolan
SCA034	The effect of sample anisotropy properties, dimensions, and imposed no-flow boundaries on the measurement of directional permeability and viscous resistivity Jacob McGregor
5:00	Closing Remarks

Alternate Orals

Alternation Orals	
SCA035	<p>Integrated Field and Core Data Analysis of Residual Oil Saturation Measurements from ASP Flooding Candidate Sandstone Reservoir in North Kuwait</p> <p>Bodoor Baroon, Chen Chao and Issa Abu Shiekah</p>
SCA036	<p>Core Preservation Materials and Techniques, Their Advantages and Limitations</p> <p>Douglas Boyd, Mohamed Al Tamimi and Hesham Shebl</p>
SCA037	<p>Advanced Image-based Workflow for 3D Pore Surface Roughness Quantification</p> <p>Yiteng Li, Xupeng He, Hyung Kwak and Hussein Hoteit</p>
SCA038	<p>Whole core scanning and Artificial intelligence for the automatic recognition of sedimentological features</p> <p>Christophe Germy, Tanguy Lhomme, Luc Perneder, Bastien Pinchard and Thomas Mazur</p>
SCA039	<p>Some Guidelines on CT-Scanning for fluid flow Visualization and Quantification</p> <p>Shameem Siddiqui</p>
SCA040	<p>The Effect of Wettability and Relative Permeability Hysteresis On Fluid Displacement in Transition Zone</p> <p>Obeida A. Tawfic</p>
SCA041	<p>Extending the limits of traditional 2 MHz NMR T1-T2 maps for source rock characterization</p> <p>Esteban Domené, Gabriela Vila1, Diana Masiero, Paula Bedini, Emilia Silletta, Manuel Velasco, Yamila Garro Linck, Belén Franzoni, Gustavo Monti and Rodolfo Acosta</p>

Posters Presentations

Posters with Manuscript	
SCA042	<p>Magnetic Core Analysis for Improved Interpretation of Potential Geothermal Prospects</p> <p>Elena Y. Temnikova, David K. Potter and Arfan Ali</p>
SCA043	<p>Application of Dielectric Measurements to Estimate Archie Parameters M and N from Drainage and Imbibition Data</p> <p>Salah Al-Ofi, Shouxiang Ma, Amer Hanif and Fei Le</p>
SCA044	<p>Gravity and flow velocity effects on fines migration in sandstone: A numerical approach in 3D with complete force set</p> <p>Shitao Liu, Igor Shikhov and Christoph Arns</p>
SCA045	<p>X-Ray Computed Tomography 3D virtual plugging – value of the technique in challenging case studies.</p> <p>Alvaro Munoz-Beltran and Stefano Pruno</p>
SCA046	<p>Complementary Models for Predicting the Formation Resistivity Factor and Resistivity Index at Overburden Conditions</p> <p>Meysam Nourani, Stefano Pruno, Mohammad Ghasemi, Muhamet Meti Fazlija, Byron Gonzalez, Jone Bråstein and Hans-Erik Rodvelt</p>
SCA047	<p>Resolving Challenges in Analyzing Iron-Rich Samples by X-Ray Diffraction</p> <p>Salah Al-Ofi and Shouxiang Ma</p>
Posters without Manuscript	
SCA048	<p>Quantitative use of dynamic 3D tomography for reservoir, CCS and environmental applications</p> <p>Nicola Bona, Leili Moghadasi, Dario Renna, Martin Barosek, Paola Allegranza, Stefano Soffientini, Laura Dovera, Ernesto Della Rossa, Alberto Guadagnini, Andrea Manzoni, Martina Siena and Aronne Dell'Oca</p>

SCA049	A complex carbonate characterization by digital rock physics and NMR methods during centrifuge desaturation Jun Gao, Xupeng He and Hyung Kwak
SCA050	Centrifuge Data Correction for Complex Carbonate Rock Samples Ahmad AlZoukani, Farhan Ali, Mohammed Al Hamad, Gallyam Aidagulov and Wael Abdallah
SCA051	Correlating the rheological properties of Pickering emulsions with the enhanced oil recovery efficiency in porous media Anastasia Strelak, Christina Ntente, Maria Theodoropoulou and Christos Tsakiroglou
SCA052	Characterization and Modeling of Hydroxyapatite Growth on Calcite Surfaces for Improved Oil Recovery Salem Alshammari, Dong Kyu Cha, Moataz Abu Alsaud, Subhash Ayirala and Ali Yousef
SCA053	Synergy between Super-Resolution and Deep Learning: An Application on Thin Sections Xupeng He, Zhen Zhang, Hyung Kwak and Hussein Hoteit
SCA054	Machine learning and artificial intelligence algorithms for geomechanical rock properties prediction based on laboratory measurements and well logs Edyta Puskarczyk, Paulina Krakowska-Madejska, Bartosz Papiernik and Grzegorz Machowski
SCA055	Dynamic elastic parameters of Jurassic deposits in the Marianowo Anticline (Poland) gas storage site with a CO ₂ cushion Paulina Krakowska-Madejska, Edyta Puskarczyk, Grzegorz Machowski, Gabriel Ząbek, Bartosz Papiernik and Michał Michna
SCA056	Integration of PCA and Clustering Analysis with Chemostratigraphy for Improved Lithofacies Characterization in Southwest Texas Andreina Liborious, Simon Hughes, Carolina Mayorga, Carl Symox and Dave Toner

SCA057	<p>Study the effect of brine salinity concentration and confining pressure on both static and dynamic properties.</p> <p>Hussain Jeshi, Adnan Makrami, Haider Albohaza and Ahmed Alqroos</p>
SCA058	<p>Experimental characterization of the chemical reactivity of wet scCO₂ in geothermal rocks under elevated temperature and pressure conditions</p> <p>Nicolás Rangel Jurado*, Xiang-Zhao Kong, Anna Kottsova, Maren Brehme, Federico Games, Stefano Bernasconi, Luiz Grafulha and Martin O. Saar</p>
SCA059	<p>Comparing Two Different NMR Based Porosity Measurements of Drill Cuttings</p> <p>M.J. Dick, D. Veselinovic, S. M. Althaus, J-H. Chen, T. Kenney and D. Green</p>
SCA060	<p>Pore Scale Modeling of Fracture Permeability Evolution Under Coupled Flow-Geochemical Process</p> <p>Xupeng He, Zhen Zhang, Hyung Kwak and Hussein Hoteit</p>
SCA061	<p>Alkali Metal Cation Specific Effects at Calcite/Brine Interfaces for Wettability Alteration</p> <p>Salem Alshammari, Hussain Saleem, Subhash Ayirala and Ali Yousef</p>
SCA062	<p>Residual Trapping during Sequestration of Supercritical CO₂ in Carbonate Saline Aquifers: A Core-Scale Experimental Study Using In-Situ Saturation Measurement Technique</p> <p>Uche Igwe, Shadrack Owusu, Amir Hossain Alizadeh and Mohammad Piri</p>
SCA063	<p>An Experimental Investigation of Three-phase Flow in a Carbonate Rock during Water-Alternating-Gas Injection Using In-Situ Saturation Measurement Technique</p> <p>Sheikh Faisal Kader Joy, Shadrack Owusu, Amir Hossain Alizadeh and Mohammad Piri</p>

SCA064	Digital Rocks Application to Refine Electrical Model of Microporous Carbonates Ivan Deshnenkov, Aqeel Furaish and Hussain Alhilal
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